

CURRENT DIAGNOSTIC APPROACHES FOR BACTERIAL MENINGITIS OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

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Annotation. *In recent years, the role of molecular diagnostic methods in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis has significantly increased. PCR and Next-generation sequencing (NGS) techniques allow for the detection of pathogens with high sensitivity and specificity, even at low concentrations in the sample. Metagenomic studies enable the identification of a wide range of pathogens without prior assumptions about the type of causative agent. Additionally, new biomarkers, such as specific proteins or metabolites, can provide further information about the nature and severity of the infection. Immunological methods, such as antibody tests, assist in diagnosing chronic or difficult-to-detect infections, such as neurosyphilis. Modern technologies for the automation and robotization of laboratory processes allow for faster test execution and improved reproducibility of results. This article reviews the latest advances in diagnostic methods for CSF analysis, with a focus on the most common CNS infections.*

Keywords: *cerebrospinal fluid, central nervous system infections, bacterial meningitis, viral meningitis, differential diagnosis, metagenomics.*

Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis remains a vital diagnostic tool for evaluating various conditions impacting the central nervous system (CNS), especially infections. Although CSF parameters such as white blood cell count, protein concentration, serum glucose ratio, and lactate levels have limited specificity, they are instrumental in distinguishing infections caused by different pathogens [1]. Traditional methods, including direct microscopy and culture, are essential for identifying causative organisms and determining their antibiotic sensitivities. Complementary diagnostic techniques, such as latex agglutination, various immunological assays, and advanced molecular methods, further enhance specificity and sensitivity [2].

CSF analysis also plays a crucial role in monitoring treatment effectiveness and early detection of infection recurrences (Figure 1). Advanced data visualization methods, such as neuroimaging, provide additional insights into the location and characteristics of inflammatory processes. These advancements position CSF analysis as not only a diagnostic tool but also a key element of personalized medicine, supporting individualized patient care. Accurate interpretation of CSF analysis requires consideration of the clinical context and accompanying data [3]. The integration of these advanced diagnostic techniques into routine clinical practice enhances treatment outcomes for patients with CNS infections.

Figure 1. Flowchart of diagnostic approach to meningitis.

In the urgent management of meningitis, it is critical to rapidly determine whether the infection is bacterial or viral to initiate appropriate antibiotic therapy immediately (Figure 1).

The link between prognosis and the timing of antibiotic administration remains uncertain. Rapid identification of bacterial meningitis (BM) relies on direct CSF examination or detection of bacterial antigens in CSF; however, these tests often exhibit limited sensitivity, failing to contribute valuable information in 30% to 50% of cases. Notably, assessing CSF parameters such as white blood cell count, protein levels, serum glucose ratio, and lactate concentration is useful for differentiating between infections caused by various pathogens. Direct examination and culture of CSF can identify the causative organisms and their antibiotic sensitivities [4]. Supplementary tests, including latex agglutination, immunological assays, and molecular techniques, offer high specificity and increasing sensitivity.

Our research underscores the importance of measuring serum procalcitonin (PCT) and CSF lactate levels to differentiate between bacterial and viral meningitis, especially when microbiological data are unavailable at the time of the patient's emergency hospital admission. Further investigation into how evaluating these two parameters affects antibiotic prescribing in meningitis patients with clear CSF, normal neurological examination, and negative direct CSF examination could provide valuable insights for clinical decision-making in emergency settings.

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